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**Sustainable and Green Electronics for Circular
Economy (SUSTRONICS)**

PROCESS VALIDATION RESULTS

VALIDATION AND TESTING RESULTS FOR
SUSTAINABLE MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF
WEARABLE SYSTEMS

WP1, T1.6

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Abstract

In this document the verification and validation process and results are described for the new proposed sustainable manufacturing process of wearable systems. Due to the fact, that the new process will not be fully implemented during the project, the validation of the concept and its sustainability are validated based on computer simulations.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In the first part of the project we have developed and proposed a completely new methodology for sustainable manufacturing process of wearable systems. In this document we will briefly summarize the innovative process and the claims that need to be validated, then the validation process will be described, followed by validation results and analysis of how these results impact the practical implementation guidelines of this process so that maximum sustainability benefits can be reached by applying it. Later in the project, based on these validation results, the final implementation guidelines will be formulated, and a proof-of-concept demonstration of the process will be executed based on these guidelines to provide an additional practical validation of the concept as well.

1.1 The process

As described in the methodology for sustainable manufacturing process of wearable systems below is the outline of the standardized steps for smart clothing manufacturing process below (see Figure 1.1) [1]:

1. Fabric rolls with an integrated universal wiring grid streamline the manufacturing process by replacing the traditional fabric selection and sourcing step;
2. The garments are subsequently tailored, produced, and sized in accordance with contemporary clothing manufacturing technologies;
3. During the seventh step of the current manufacturing process, known as fabric-joining, additional connectors are incorporated as needed to link wiring between separate cut components, such as attaching sleeves to the torso of a shirt;
4. In the garment finishing phase, which is the eighth step of the manufacturing process, a connector or pocket is incorporated to house a module containing a battery and a wireless communication unit;

Figure 1.1: Proposed standardized steps for smart clothing manufacturing process [1]

5. In the same step, sensor nodes are selected and strategically placed at appropriate locations on the finished garment, transforming it into a functional sensor network;
6. During the ninth step, which involves quality control and assurance, the entire garment undergoes comprehensive testing. Self-diagnosis and mapping are conducted to determine the optimal wiring for power, data, and clock signal delivery, ensuring that all components function correctly;
7. Following the completion of the final touches, which is the tenth step of the manufacturing process, the smart clothing is dispatched to the user. Along with the garment, the user receives software that enables them to configure the required functionalities of the garment, such as loading sensor or actuator drivers across the entire sensor network for seamless integration;
8. Finally, the data collected from the sensor network is aggregated and potentially pre-processed by the main communication module. This data is then wirelessly transmitted to a computer or mobile device, where additional software can be deployed to address specific use-case requirements.

This proposed process is built on top of modern clothing manufacturing technology [2] and have the following differences/updates as shown in Table 1.1.

Original step	Changes	Details
1. Planning	No change	-
2. Fabric selection and sourcing	Replaced	New fabric manufactured
3. Garment accessory, trim and closure selection	No change	-
4. Garment sizing and fit	No change	-
5. Pattern construction	No change	-
6. Fabric spreading and cutting	No change	-
7. Fabric-joining	Updated	Wire joining procedure added
8. Garment finishing	Updated	Sensor node and base station connection step added
9. Quality control and quality assurance	Updated	Wiring mapping and testing procedure added
10. Final touches	No change	-

Table 1.1: Proposed changes in the steps of modern clothing manufacturing technology

Chapter 2

Validation methodology

Due to the fact, that this methodology aims at completely new wearables manufacturing process, the actual process will not be fully implemented during the project and will instead be developed as a theoretical framework with limited proof-of-concept piloting instead. Thus, only the plausibility of implementation will be validated through practical implementation in pilot (creation of interconnect fabric, cutting and sewing the fabric into a wearable form, adding wearable sensor nodes and interconnecting the data flows). The rest of the testing of this methodology takes place as computer simulation in order to prove the efficiency and sustainability of the interconnect approach.

The first plausibility tests have been done in the lab in a small scale with a simple wired data and power transmission proof of concept. Further physical process validation will be done in the next iterations of pilot prototypes.

Additionally, the efficiency and sustainability of the approach has been analysed using computer simulations. Specifically, to determine answers to the following questions:

- What is the overall plausibility of implementation of this process?
- What is the reachability of any randomly placed wearable node on the interconnect?
- What is the percentage of useful vs redundant interconnect lanes in any random wearable configuration?
- What is the average length and number of jumps in the interconnect between any two random wearable nodes?
- What is the efficiency of use of the interconnect material (e.g. copper)

2.1 Simulations

In order to answer the previously defined questions a set of simulations was developed. The simulation methodology contained the following steps, as described next.

2.1.1 Generation and marking of clothing items

In order to prove, that any specific topology of smart textile wiring can provide useful results for a wide variety of real-world smart clothing applications, we first need to develop a representative set of clothing item schematics, that can be simulated to be cut and sewn from each of the smart textile configurations being analyzed.

A selection of **17 different clothing designs** was selected as follows (the selection was limited to the available schematics, but wide enough to cover main types of clothing that might be used as smart clothing):

- Male garments:
 - Fitted T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - * with V-neck, short arms
 - * with V-neck, long arms
 - Wide cut T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - Jacket/Hoodie
 - Shorts
- Female garments:
 - Fitted T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - * with V-neck, short arms
 - * with V-neck, long arms
 - Wide cut T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - Jacket/Hoodie
 - Shorts
 - Pants/Leggings

An example clothing schematic (Male T-Shirt with Long Arms) can be seen in Figure 2.1.

For each of these clothing schematics not only all cuts were defined, but also the edges that need to be sewn together on each of the cut pieces were marked (see Figure 2.2), so that during the simulation the actual connectivity across the

Figure 2.1: Example of clothing schematic used in simulation

Figure 2.2: Example of marked sewn joint in clothing schematic

Size	Male Chest circumference	Female Chest circumference
XXS	70–78	66–74
XS	78–86	74–82
S	86–94	82–90
M	94–102	90–98
L	102–110	98–107
XL	110–118	107–119
XXL	118–129	119–131
3XL	129–141	131–143
4XL	141–154	143–155
5XL	154–166	155–167

Table 2.1: Different clothing sizes (in mm) used for simulations

connections of multiple pieces of smart textile can be evaluated, not only each piece by itself.

Each clothing item was then generated into **10 different sizes** according to European standard BSI, 2004. BS EN 13402-3:2004 "Size Designation of Clothes - Part 3: Measurements and Intervals" as shown in Table 2.1.

Thus in total for simulations $17 * 10 =$ **170 different clothing schematics** were prepared.

2.1.2 Selection of candidate wiring schematics for simulation

In order to simulate different applicable wiring patterns for smart textiles, representative and useful patterns must be selected first. Due to the fact, that one of the goals is sustainability and thus minimization of wiring material used, it must be noted, that **all wire segments should be straight** as that is the shortest route between two points and thus yields the shortest wire length. Also, due to the fact, that the process must be applicable to all kinds of clothing, without any preference for specific cutting schematics and rotations, the **pattern should be symmetrical rotationally**, which means that **all wire segments should be of the same length**.

As the wiring pattern in total can be looked at as a tessellation of the plane of the smart textile, and more specifically, we are interested in the wires (edges) not the tessellating figures themselves. When looking at a rotationally symmetrical group of wires/edges, we can look at the vertex connecting those edges, and thus analyze the patterns based on the vertexes and how many of these equal length wires connect to them at what angles. The vertex symmetry of interest is called isogonality.

As there are an infinite number of such tessellations or wire patterns possible, so some additional constraints must be added. The tessellations must not "waste" wires, by having concave tessellation shapes. When evaluating a type of tessellation, that matches all these requirements, it was determined, that a good candidate is equilateral monogonal tessellations. There are 11 Archimedean (semi-regular) tessellations forming only regular shapes such as squares etc. (a more

Figure 2.3: Selected wiring patterns/tessellations for simulation

detailed description of the choice is available in [3]), so a selection of tessellation shapes with these properties were chosen as shown in Figure 2.3. Each of the tessellation patterns has a name with numbers separated with points, where the numbers mean what shape connects to the vertex (e.g. 3=triangle, 4=square, 6=hexagon). Thus a 6.6.6 pattern means that each vertex connects to 3 regular hexagons, while 4.4.4.4 pattern means that each vertex connects to 4 squares. Some regular shapes can be arranged in multiple ways around a vertex forming a different tessellation pattern - two additional such modifications were found for the pattern 4.6.12 and those are marked with additional letters "a" and "b" accordingly, resulting in $11 + 2 = 13$ **different wiring patterns** selected for simulations.

The minimum and maximum length of those wire segments must also be determined for the simulations. Most clothing is either for top or bottom half of the human body, and a reasonable maximum human height is about 2 meters, thus, half of that or 1 meter is a reasonable upper limit for a height of a clothing item, and thus a piece of smart textile needed for it. As humans are usually not wider than a meter, we can assume for simplicities sake, that the maximum dimensions of a piece of smart textile needed for human clothing should be about 1m by 1m or 1000mm by 1000mm. Because of this a single wire should be somewhere between 0mm and 1000mm based on the number of sensor attachment points that might be needed across the smart clothing item. We can assume, that it is possible to connect a sensor or actuator module to the wires on smart clothing with some sort of minimal length of connector - for the simulation we assume that this connector/jumper wire can be up to 10mm long. From that

the minimum wire length can be assumed double that due to the fact, that if a node is connected between two ends of the shortest wire, these jumper wires could still connect to at least one of the ends. Thus, the **minimum wire length used in simulations is 20mm**. On the other hand, the maximum wire length should be no longer than any reasonable distance between two wearable sensors on potential smart clothing. A typical human motion analysis application might require a sensor per each large human joint (e.g. one on lower and upper arm respectively). On most humans this distance falls somewhere between 150mm-300mm. In order to be conservative, for the simulations we target the lower end of this distance, so around 150mm. In order to reduce the simulation calculation length, we can use a doubling scale for the wire lengths - thus starting from 20mm, we can double the lengths to 40mm, 80mm and finally 160mm (around 150mm mentioned before). This leads to **4 different wire lengths** to be used for simulation.

As a result the simulation has $13 * 4 = 52$ **different wiring patterns in multiple wire lengths**. In order to run simulations for each wire pattern on each selected clothing schematic, we need to run $52 * 170 = 8840$ **different simulated experiments**.

2.1.3 Simulation methodology

To finalize the number of simulated experiments to be run, one more parameter must be determined - the allowable distance between a sensor and wire or between two wires across two sewn together pieces of fabric, referred to as jumper length (see Figure 2.4). As discussed before, the minimum reasonable jumper length can be assumed to be 10mm. The maximum jumper length should not be reasonably longer than, the maximum wire length, so using the same doubling approach as for wire length, we can arrive at the following **5 jumper lengths** to be used in the simulations: 10mm, 20mm, 40mm, 80mm and 160mm.

Finally, we can define our experimental simulation parameter space for each simulated experiment with each jumper length to be $8840 * 5 = 44200$ **different simulations to be run**.

For each of these simulations then results will be aggregated and analyzed in order to select the most appropriate wiring configurations.

Figure 2.4: Examples of jumper wires for smart textiles (green) connecting wires between multiple parts of clothing or wires to sensor nodes (blue)

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Simulation execution time

Due to the high amount of complex calculations needed for these simulations, the computing time required was quite high. It was estimated, that the total compute time on a reasonably modern server hardware in a single thread would amount to **4.61 years**.

To reduce the compute time, the simulation was adjusted to be able to run in a multi threaded setting on multiple CPU cores. This allowed to reduce the theoretical simulation completion time to **52.68 days** on a 32 core server. To make the execution time more practical withing the boundaries of the project, the simulation was split among 6 servers with 32 cores each - this reduced the theoretical simulation execution time to just **8.78 days**.

It was determined, that depending on the specific configuration, a single simulation could take up to **15.12 hours**.

Unfortunately, some of the simulation configurations were more compute intensive than others. This led to disbalance between executing server load, resulting in a spread between server execution time between **5 days, 11 hours, 25 minutes** and **9 days, 15 hours, 51 minutes**.

This led to the final simulation execution time of **10 days, 17 minutes and 44 seconds**, meaning that due to unbalanced server and core workload an extra **1 day, 5 hours, 34 minutes and 36 seconds** were used above the theoretical execution time.

3.2 Simulated parameters

For each of the configurations a Monte Carlo simulation of multiple randomized point pairs was used to simulate a distribution of multiple measurements related to each configuration. For each of the measurements the following statistical summaries were acquired:

- Maximum value with 95% confidence intervals;

- Median value with 95% confidence intervals;
- Distribution with the following percentile values:
 - 5th percentile;
 - 10th percentile;
 - 25th percentile;
 - 50th percentile (Median value);
 - 75th percentile;
 - 90th percentile;
 - 95th percentile.

The acquired measurements for each of the simulation runs are as follows:

- The total length of wires;
- The total number and length of jumpers generated;
- The total amount of nodes;
- Number of reachable nodes in the wiring configuration;
- Length of reachable wire segments in the wiring configuration;
- Reachable jumper length and count;
- Then for two separate optimization algorithms (Shortest Path and Path with Least number of Jumpers needed) the following measurements were recorded:
 - Percentage of useful nodes, that are actually needed for routing signals;
 - Percentage of useful wire length, that are actually needed for routing signals;
 - Percentage of reachable sensors from all sensor locations attempted in the simulation;
 - Percentage of useful jumper count and length used for reaching the sensors;
 - Percentage of sensors that are unreachable due to the fact that simulated jumper length is too short;
 - Number of nodes that can be reached through multiple paths;
 - Length of the longest simulated path between sensors;
 - Number of nodes in the simulated path with most nodes;
 - Number of jumpers in the simulated path with most jumpers;
 - The maximum length of a jumper wire needed to connect a sensor to the wire grid;

- The maximum number of branches a single node needs to route in this simulation run;
- The overall wire length, jumper count and node count in the simulated wire network.

3.3 Selecting the best configuration based on simulation results

In order to select the best wiring configuration for the project, first two key parameters of each configuration were analyzed:

1. The total length of wires used for the average clothing item in that configuration - the less wires are used, the more sustainable the process, as the configuration requires less expensive materials to be used for wiring;
2. The percentage of simulated sensor configurations, that were actually reachable after the interconnect is cut and sewn in a clothing. The higher the reachability, the more practical the process will be and the more adaptation it will see - this is due to the fact, that if a sensor cannot be attached to the smart clothing in the needed location (and thus cannot be reached in use) the overall usefulness of the process is reduced, that would lead to lower number of users, and thus less benefit from economies of scale, leading to more ineffectiveness.

While looking at these two key measurements for all of the simulated configurations, the data showed a clear tradeoff between these two measures. The longer the overall total wire length, the higher the reachability. Still there is room for optimal configuration selection. As can be seen in Figure 3.1 initially the reachability grows rapidly with the increase of the total wire length, but tapers down at around 80% reachability. On the other hand, the total wire length explodes exponentially after around 80 meter mark, making it even less sustainable to use those higher length wire configurations.

Even though it is tempting to narrow down the candidate configurations based on the averages of these two measures across the board, in fact there are quite big deviations between configurations using different jumper lengths. This is because, a long jumper length can compensate for an inappropriately sparse interconnect. Thus, to further narrow down the most sustainable wiring configurations of the total 52 wiring pattern/length configurations, we must first look separately at the results for each of five jumper lengths.

In order to select the most appropriate configurations we must select a range of sensor node reachability that will be acceptable in order to select the candidate patterns. As a lower bound we select 95% reachability, meaning, that only 1 in 20 sensor nodes on average might not be reachable on the smart garment. In order to also minimize the maximum wire length used for the smart clothing items, we will **define pattern efficiency** as the ratio of reachability improvement per meter of wire spent. For each of the jumper lengths we select the wiring

Figure 3.1: Tradeoff between the total simulated wire length of wire configurations vs the reachability percentage of the simulated sensor placement.

configuration with the best pattern efficiency, which necessarily minimizes the amount of wire material spent for the required reachability and thus should provide the most sustainable interconnect pattern.

As shown in Figures 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 respectively for all five jumper lengths, the key parameter interactions are as follows:

- 10mm jumper: this jumper length results in only 2 wiring patterns, that provide 95%+ sensor node reachability. Of these, the most efficient pattern is 3.3.3.3.3.3 with 40mm wire length between nodes which on average provides 97.9% reachability and on average requires 103.8m of wiring;
- 20mm jumper: this jumper length results in 16 wiring patterns, that provide 95%+ sensor node reachability. Of these, the most efficient pattern is 3.3.3.3.3.3 with 80mm wire length between nodes which on average provides 97.6% reachability and on average requires 51.8m of wiring;
- 40mm jumper: this jumper length results in 29 wiring patterns, that provide 95%+ sensor node reachability. Of these, the most efficient pattern is 3.3.3.3.3.3 with 160mm wire length between nodes which on average provides 96.1% reachability and on average requires 25.8m of wiring;
- 80mm jumper: this jumper length results in 40 wiring patterns, that provide 95%+ sensor node reachability. Of these, the most efficient pattern is 4.4.4.4 with 160mm wire length between nodes which on average provides 98.6% reachability and on average requires 14.9m of wiring;
- 160mm jumper: this jumper length results in 45 wiring patterns, that provide 95%+ sensor node reachability. Of these, the most efficient pattern is 3.6.3.6 with 160mm wire length between nodes which on average provides 96.4% reachability and on average requires 12.9m of wiring;

Figure 3.2: Tradeoff between the total simulated wire length vs the reachability percentage using 10mm jumpers only.

3.4 Selection of the best wire and jumper length for the selected configuration

The previously described simulation results show, that the specific selection of the most sustainable interconnect pattern might depend on the scale of the pattern (length of single wire sections) and maximum allowed jumper lengths.

Thus, the simulations were explored for each of the three candidate interconnect patterns in relation to both single wire section length (one of the 4 lengths discussed above: 20mm, 40mm, 80mm and 160mm) and to maximum jumper length (one of the 5 lengths discussed above: 10mm, 20mm, 40mm, 80mm and 160mm).

For each of these patterns the pattern efficiency score was calculated (multiplied per 1000 meters of wire used for readability) and plotted as shown in Figures 3.7, 3.8 and 3.9.

From this analysis we can group the wire section lengths in three categories as shown in Figure 3.10 - category A, where the most sustainable pattern is 3.6.3.6, category B, where the most sustainable pattern is 4.4.4.4 and category C where the most sustainable pattern is 3.3.3.3.3.3.

For a complete picture, we also need to take into account the tradeoff for these parameters and patterns related to the reachability. Specifically as we want to provide at least 95% reachability. This can be seen in Figures 3.11, 3.12 and 3.13.

When joining the two criteria together - the minimum sensor reachability of 95% and the efficient use of wire to achieve this reachability, we arrive at a more complete picture of when each of the configurations is the most efficient as shown in Figure ?? - category A, where the most sustainable pattern is 3.6.3.6, category B, where the most sustainable pattern is 4.4.4.4, category C where the most sustainable pattern is 3.3.3.3.3.3 and category D, where 95% reachability

Figure 3.3: Tradeoff between the total simulated wire length vs the reachability percentage using 20mm jumpers only.

Figure 3.4: Tradeoff between the total simulated wire length vs the reachability percentage using 40mm jumpers only.

Figure 3.5: Tradeoff between the total simulated wire length vs the reachability percentage using 80mm jumpers only.

Figure 3.6: Tradeoff between the total simulated wire length vs the reachability percentage using 160mm jumpers only.

Figure 3.7: Configuration 3.3.3.3.3 efficiency in relation to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.8: Configuration 4.4.4.4 efficiency in relation to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.9: Configuration 3.6.3.6 efficiency in relation to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.10: Configuration efficiency categories - A (best for 3.6.3.6), B (best for 4.4.4.4) and C (best for 3.3.3.3.3) as relating to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.11: Configuration 3.3.3.3.3 reachability in relation to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.12: Configuration 4.4.4.4 reachability in relation to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.13: Configuration 3.6.3.6 reachability in relation to wire section and jumper lengths.

Figure 3.14: Configuration efficiency categories with 95%+ reachability- A (best for 3.6.3.6), B (best for 4.4.4.4), C (best for 3.3.3.3.3.3) and D (not usable) as relating to wire section and jumper lengths.

cannot be supported and thus these configurations should not be used.

Overall this shows, that in configurations which allow longer maximum jumper length, the most sustainable is the 3.6.3.6. interconnect configuration, but in situations where maximum jumper length is smaller, it might become more sustainable to use 4.4.4.4 or in some rare cases even 3.3.3.3.3.3 interconnect patterns.

3.5 Answering the simulation questions

Finally, for the validation tests for the selected most sustainable configuration (3.6.3.6 with 160mm jumper length maximum and 160mm wire section length) the results to the posed testing and validation questions were as follows:

- What is the reachability of any randomly placed wearable node on the interconnect?
 - The overall reachability of randomly placed wearable nodes on this

interconnect configuration is 96.37% (mean) with standard deviation of 10.4%. The percentiles of this statistic are:

- * 25th = 99.39%,
- * 50th (median) = 99.82%,
- * 75th = 99.99%

- What is the percentage of useful vs redundant interconnect lanes in any random wearable configuration?

- The overall percentage of useful vs redundant interconnect lanes in any random wearable configuration 58.86% (mean) with standard deviation of 5.89%. The percentiles of this statistic are:

- * 25th = 57.06%,
- * 50th (median) = 59.15%,
- * 75th = 62.47%

- What is the average length and number of jumps in the interconnect between any two random wearable nodes?

- The average length of wire in the interconnect between two random wearable nodes is 769mm (mean) with standard deviation of 171mm. The percentiles of this statistic are:

- * 25th = 632mm,
- * 50th (median) = 762mm,
- * 75th = 868mm

- The average number of jumps in the interconnect between two random wearable nodes is 6.1 (mean) with standard deviation of 1.3. The percentiles of this statistic are:

- * 25th = 5.0,
- * 50th (median) = 6.0,
- * 75th = 6.9

- What is the efficiency of use of the interconnect material (e.g. copper)?

- The overall efficiency of the interconnect material measured as reachability percent of sensor nodes per 1000m of interconnect total material used is 100% (mean) with standard deviation of 56%. The percentiles of this statistic are:

- * 25th = 57%,
- * 50th (median) = 87%,
- * 75th = 100

Chapter 4

Analysis

The results of simulation based testing and validation of the interconnect configuration sustainability lead to several key findings, as described in this section.

4.1 Jumper length tradeoffs

Overall, the results show, that there is a direct tradeoff between the maximum length of allowed connection jumpers and the average expenditure of wiring for the interconnect. More specifically, the total wire length grows exponentially if the jumper length is reduced below 40mm, but becomes almost static for jumper lengths of at least 80mm or more as shown in Figure 4.1.

Additionally, the Jumper length directly impacts the efficiency of the interconnect pattern - longer maximum jumper lengths lead to more efficient and sustainable interconnect patterns. This variable in combination with maximum single wire section length allows the implementers to select the most efficient and sustainable interconnect pattern for their needs as shown in Figure 3.10.

4.2 Pattern manufacturing efficiency and sustainability

The validation results also imply an interesting finding - the interconnect patterns, that are simpler to manufacture are also more efficient and sustainable from the reachability and wire use perspective. Specifically - this is true from two key aspects:

- Wire/cable straightness;
- Inter-wire/cable connector complexity.

These aspects are explored below.

Figure 4.1: The impact of maximum jumper length and the total length of wires in the interconnect.

4.2.1 Wire/cable straightness

A very interesting emerging property of the wiring patterns that were determined to be the most efficient and sustainable, is the fact that of the 13 wiring patterns, these three are the only ones, that can be manufactured by using only uninterrupted straight lines of wiring. Every other pattern requires some sort of bends or interruptions in the wiring lines. This is interesting not only from the mathematical perspective of straight lines being easier to use to cover the whole surface of the smart clothing, but also due to the fact, that most existing machines currently usable for adding conductive threads to fabric, such as sewing or printing, use the least energy to create straight lines. This is thus promising also from the manufacturing perspective, not only the reachability and wire economy perspective.

4.2.2 Inter-wire/cable connector complexity

Additionally, from the sustainability perspective, if the interconnect wiring requires cables with multiple wires inside, the connectors between these cables are simpler to manufacture in pattern 3.6.3.6 or 4.4.4.4 requiring only n clamps (where n is the number of wires per cable), while the 3.3.3.3.3 configuration requires $3*n$ clamps instead as shown in the example images below illustrating $n=4$ case with 3.6.3.6 configuration (Figure 4.2), 4.4.4.4 configuration (Figure 4.3) and 3.3.3.3.3 configuration (Figure 4.4).

This is interesting also, because more complex shapes like hexagons in configuration 6.6.6 also require the more complex $3*n$ clamps as shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.2: Cable connector with 4 wires and 4 clamps (3.6.3.6).

Figure 4.3: Cable connector with 4 wires and 4 clamps (4.4.4.4).

Figure 4.4: Cable connector with 4 wires and 12 clamps (3.3.3.3.3).

Figure 4.5: Cable connector with 4 wires and 12 clamps (6.6.6).

4.3 Sustainability of the proposed methodology

The overall simulation based tests have validated the concept of the interconnect based methodology and demonstrated, that high efficiency and reachability can be achieved with relatively minimal use of material, thus proving that the selected interconnect configuration is more sustainable than other dismissed configurations while at the same time, it is practical enough to be used in most smart clothing manufacturing scenarios, thus leading to sustainability of implementation of this methodology by minimal replacement of equipment and training that is currently used in the standard modern clothing manufacturing methodology.

As mentioned previously **Sustainability** is a critical consideration for this proposed methodology. Any processes that force replacement of existing equipment will have major environmental impact on such a scale, which might also impede adoption of such a standard due to climate change considerations and legislation. Even though other approaches for reducing the environmental effect of smart textiles are being explored, such as circular economy and recycling [4], the environmental impact of clothing manufacturing processes cannot be underestimated [5], and when innovations are applied with care, even the growth of textile and clothing manufacturing industry, can lead to reduction in carbon-dioxide emissions[6]. In order to make a supply chain for smart clothing sustainable, it has to be built on a closed-loop mode that starts from material production and ends with recycling [7]. It has taken a lot of resources and time to move the classic clothing industry towards these goals, thus, reuse of any part of this supply chain will greatly reduce the investments needed to make smart clothing manufacturing sustainable. The proposed methodology minimizes the changes to the established clothing manufacturing process, thus minimizing environmental costs of the process implementation.

At the same time the discreet and defined steps of the improved process allow for additional process optimization at every step – for example, the material and wiring embedding process can be optimized on an industrial scale, where each sustainability improvement and cost reduction scales and motivates the manufacturer as opposed to the existing processes, where each specific item of smart clothing is a small scale manufacturing with many inefficiencies and the low amount of items produced does not support optimizations of mass production, thus more wasteful processes were forced to be used.

The methodology defines a manufacturing process in which the core improvement is based on the use and configuration of the interconnect fabric, which allows for incremental improvements in the discreet manufacturing steps. The new process allows for previously impossible sustainability improvements in the smart clothing manufacturing process itself. Specifically, because many different manufacturers are currently forced to reinvent the wheel and use unique non-standardized low-yield processes for each smart clothing item type manufacturing. This means more material waste due to lack of scale and high amount of manufacturing failures due to unreliable and even manual processes. This also means, that during the manufacturing the smart clothing items might

need to be shipped long distances between different specialists (clothing, wiring, fashion, electronics, sensors, washability etc.) introducing environmental costs of this extra shipping. This can be solved by allowing for universal adaptation of complex and highly resilient wearable interconnect technologies as well as development of new even better ones, while allowing the manufacturers of smart clothing to spend less time, effort and materials in order to develop new smart clothing items with unique and useful functionality [8]. This problem is exacerbated even more by the fact that the existing clothing manufacturing industry is very large in the scale of investments and equipment deployed - on the trillion-dollar scale (1.53 trillion USD in 2022[9]), thus each new type of manufacturing process for smart clothing necessitates a lot of replaced and adjusted equipment leading to even more waste.

The implementation of this proposed standard allows for optimization in each standardized step and removes the overlap of specialties required for manufacturing a new type of smart clothing – existing clothing experts can keep their work processes and machinery, and only some steps of the conventional clothing manufacturing process need to be updated for the new process to work. Each of these isolated steps can then be optimized in order to maximize the sustainability of smart clothing manufacturing in the future. The simulations and prototypes for the process validation developed in this project also allow us to provide specific guidelines to implement the process appropriately with most sustainability in mind for a specific application/production of smart clothing.

The new methodology allows a selection of specific wiring configurations applicable for a specific need, that offer the best efficiency and sustainability in such measures as reachability of sensor nodes independent of cuts in the fabric, minimized expenditure of wires, relatively easy interconnect manufacturing using straight lines for wiring and simple low cost cable connectors.

Because of the aforementioned and the fact that the smart clothing market is predicted to grow rapidly (and even predicted to exceed the mobile phone market) [10] it can be assumed to be the future of wearable sensing, capable of delivering a higher order of magnitude beneficial impact than previous wearable technologies. This instead means that with increased scale of production all wasteful aspects in manufacturing have much greater impact on sustainability, and any improvements in recycle-ability or longevity of the products as well as in the manufacturing process would have a great sustainability impact.

A big problem currently with the previously mentioned underdeveloped factors of smart clothing related to washability, manufacturability and robustness to wear and tear have serious sustainability/environmental implications due to the fact, that the less resistant to use and washing the manufactured item is, the shorter its effective life and the faster it turns into waste, thus increasing the environmental impact. Thus any improvements in these areas can significantly impact the sustainability of smart clothing manufacturing and use.

Existing state-of-art wireless BANs introduce two additional sustainability problems - (1) each wireless device or sensor requires its own batteries, meaning that more rare earth materials must be used for manufacturing more batteries

and more resources are wasted on battery charging which is an inefficient process, especially in the case of wireless charging; (2) energy efficiency of wireless transmissions is usually worse than planned, due to the fact that other devices might be transmitting at the same time and place, thus leading to collisions and interference, which in turn leads to more power spent on the wireless transmissions in order to successfully send and receive them, especially in crowded areas. If wireless transmission can be replaced where possible with wired alternatives, less wasted energy would be used, thus increasing sustainability of the solution.

Finally, the highest current sustainability impact of smart clothing manufacturing is in the manufacturing process itself. Many different manufacturers are forced to reinvent the wheel and use unique non-standardized low-yield processes for each smart clothing item type. This means more material waste due to lack of scale and high amount of manufacturing failures due to unreliable and even manual processes. This also means, that during the manufacturing the smart clothing items might need to be shipped long distances between different specialists (clothing, wiring, fashion, electronics, sensors, washability etc.) introducing environmental costs of this extra shipping. This can be solved by allowing for universal adaptation of complex and highly resilient wearable interconnect technologies as well as development of new even better ones, while allowing the manufacturers of smart clothing to spend less time, effort and materials in order to develop new smart clothing items with unique and useful functionality [8]. This problem is exacerbated even more by the fact that the existing clothing manufacturing industry is very large in the scale of investments and equipment deployed - on the trillion dollar scale (1.53 trillion USD in 2022[9]), thus each new type of manufacturing process for smart clothing necessitates a lot of replaced and adjusted equipment leading to even more waste.

The proposed process builds on the existing manufacturing process as much as possible, minimizing the requirements for equipment replacement or more complex manufacturing steps that might reduce adoption and thus maximizing the potential benefits from economies of scale and efficiency of the selected wiring configurations.

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